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Content Analysis of Stories for Preschoolers About Honesty*

Sibel Dal¹, Cemil Öztep²

¹ Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University, Alanya, Antalya, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0003-2319-4656

² Doğankent Anatolian Imam Hatip High School, Adana, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0002-1768-8046

Correspondence: Sibel DAL, Faculty of Education, Department of Primary Education, Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University, Alanya, Antalya, Turkey. E-mail: sibel.dal@alanya.edu.tr

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine how selected stories, which are written in Turkish by local or foreign authors for preschoolers, deal with honesty. In this basic interpretive qualitative study, data were collected through document analysis and analyzed through content analysis. Analyzed documents are twenty-one picture books, which written in Turkish for preschoolers published between 2004 and 2015, nine stories about honesty published online by four Turkish Provincial Directorates of National Education and one story about honesty published online by the Center for Values Education. The software NVivo 11 was used to conduct computer-assisted data analysis. The results of this study demonstrate that most of the analyzed texts use “dishonesty and its negative consequences” more than “honesty and its positive outcomes” to promote honesty.

Keywords: Honesty, Preschool, Picture Book, Online Story, Content Analysis

1. Introduction

Classic fairy tales are listened to with pleasure by preschool children and transmitted from one generation to the next. Picture books with unique stories are important in terms of the contributions they can make to the development of children. The stories to be read to children can have many purposes such a supporting the linguistic and cognitive development of children, presenting them with information about life, developing their imagination, supporting their creativity, entertaining them, and making it possible for them to acquire a love of reading (Karatay, 2007). Additionally, parents and teachers can contribute to children’s learning by extending the stories to the situations children are experiencing, using the stories as a jumping board for important discussions (Stribling, 2008). Another potential benefit of stories is the acquisition of values. Stories have long been one of the tools used to teach children certain values.

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1.1 Teaching Values with Stories

The use of stories is frequently encountered in values education activities included in the values education guides for pre-school education prepared by some provincial directorates of national education (DNE) such as Antalya, Batman, Gaziantep, Malatya in Turkey (Antalya Provincial Directorate of National Education [AntalyaDNE], 2013; Batman Provincial Directorate of National Education [BatmanDNE], 2015; Gaziantep Provincial Directorate of National Education [GaziantepDNE], 2014; Malatya Provincial Directorate of National Education [MalatyaDNE], 2012). In addition, it is common to find preschool-level books written for value education. The specific values reinforced in value education guides for preschool children, as well as picture book sets on values, vary, but honesty is one value that is reinforced.

1.2 Messages of Stories

It is not hard to guess that stories written for small children which deal directly with the main theme of honesty carry a message such as, "being honest is a right and desired behavior." However, stories naturally carry many messages which can be influenced by the point of view of the writer and the characteristics of the listener. These messages which are clearly emphasized in the story and transmitted with a clear message may not always be directed at the desired goals of education. To give an example from one of the known classic stories, there is the message that there is nothing wrong with the victim (giant) in the fairy-tale called Jack and the Beanpole being robbed and killed. It can be stated that there is the message in the fairy-tale called Cinderella that being beautiful is sufficient to make a vertical jump in social status (Jacobs, 2014). Additionally, some hidden messages can also be found in these stories. For example, in the way that characters are depicted or the choice of words used in dialogue, such as praise for kingship, women being shown as weak or the source of evil, and the sudden solution of the problems through magic without spending any effort. Through the analysis of the components used by the writer dealing with the theme of honesty while constructing the story, an understanding can be developed as to what messages are transmitted to the children while supporting the value of honesty, the narration style of why children need to behave honestly, whether negative examples are presented to the children and, how the theme of honesty is dealt with. In this respect, the problem of the study consists of how stories about honesty, written for preschool children in Turkish, deal with the subject of honesty.

1.3 Research Question

The major research question of this study is as follows:

"How do Turkish language stories about honesty, written for preschool children, deal with the subject of honesty?"

Upon conducting a review of the literature, no studies on how the value of honesty is dealt with in Turkish young children's literature were found. The most important study which inspired this study which dealt with the theme of honesty in picture books was Lee, Talwar, McCarthy, Ross, Evans and Arruda (2014) which examined the effects of classic stories about honesty on children. The study included participants aged three to seven. Lee et al. (2014) concluded that the children gave more honest answers when a story emphasizing the positive consequences of honesty was read before asking questions compared to a story emphasizing the negative consequences of lying. Taking this as the starting point, this study aims to present how the value of honesty is dealt with in Turkish stories with the theme of honesty written for preschool children.

1.4 Objective of the Study

The following subquestions support the overall research question, how do Turkish language stories about honesty, written for preschool children, deal with the subject of honesty:

1. What is the frequency of examples of honest behavior?
2. What is shown as the reason for behaving honestly?
3. What is the outcome of behaving honestly?

4. What is the frequency of examples of dishonest behavior?
5. Why do characters behave dishonestly?
6. What are the consequences of not behaving honestly?

2. Method

This study was carried out using the basic qualitative research design (Merriam, 2013). In this study, the researchers tried to understand and interpret how the value of honesty was dealt with in Turkish stories on honesty written for preschool children.

2.1 Study Group

The study group was determined through the criterion sampling method which is one of the purposeful sampling methods. Within this scope, the stories to be used as sources of data were determined in line with these criteria: (i) Being written for preschool children, (ii) being in the Turkish language and (iii) being clear that they deal with the theme of honesty. As a result of material compilation carried out with these criteria, the study group consisted of 21 children's picture books published between the years 2004-2015 which dealt with the theme of honesty, written for preschool children, published in Turkish and written by Turkish or foreign writers; 9 stories published online within the scope of value education by some provincial directorate for national education (Antalya DNE, 2013; Batman DNE, 2015; Gaziantep DNE, 2014; Malatya DNE, 2012) and one story published on the website of Center for Values Education (CVE).

2.2 Collection and Analysis of Data

In this study, the data were obtained through the document analysis technique. For the analysis of data, qualitative content analysis technique (Elo, Kääriäinen, Kanste, Pölkki, Utriainen, and Kyngäs, 2014; Schreier, 2014) was used. Qualitative content analysis requires the whole content to be read carefully (Forman and Damschroder, 2008). According to Schreier (2014, p. 174), the qualitative content analysis consists of these stages: deciding on the study question, selecting material, creating a codes framework, trial codes, evaluation of the code framework and its organization, analysis of the data, presentation and interpretation of the findings.

Taking all these processes related to qualitative content analysis, this study aimed to create a vision about the data which can be categorized and the codes to be done after the identification of picture books and online stories which can answer the study question and all the stories were read by one of the researchers. A coding framework was created based on the analyzed stories. Within this scope, the same researcher prepared the "Honesty Value Analysis Table" created based on the stories and the MS Excel 2013 program. Expert opinions were asked to evaluate and organize this code framework and the code framework was rearranged by the other researcher. This first stage was done by hand the stories were analyzed with the "Honesty Value Analysis Table" and the trial codes were carried out in this manner. In the next stage of the study, the trial codes were analyzed using the QSR NVivo 11 program. In this stage, the codes in the "Honesty Value Analysis Table" were reviewed, the number of sub-titles for code was increased, codes were given their final shape upon the agreement of the researchers and the stories were reviewed once again.

As a result of the analysis, two main categories emerged as "honesty centered" and "behaving dishonestly centered." Each component of these two main categories was accepted as sub-categories. In the presentation of the findings, the picture books and online stories were dealt with under separate titles. In the presentation of each category and the codes, direct quotations were given place from the picture books and online stories. Since the books were published in Turkish, the researchers included direct quotations in the study by translating them into English. In the presentation of the quotations, "the picture books" were coded as PS and "the online stories" were coded as OS and all stories were numbered.

2.3 Reliability of the Study

In the study, the researchers gave the care to describe in detail the application carried out for reliability at every stage of the research. To decrease the subjective state of the researchers on the findings related to time, the data were analyzed at two different times by the researchers. For the verification of the data obtained from the study, the list of the analyzed books in the study was presented, quotations from the stories were given in the findings section and expert opinions were asked about the findings. In the creation of the categories and codes, firstly a trial code was done with 8 books (about 25% of the study group). As the number of the analyzed stories increased, the code framework changed and this necessitated the reanalysis of the stories which were analyzed before. The Honesty Value Analysis Table was formed and the views of two faculty members who work in the areas of preschool education and value education, a faculty member who works in the areas of primary school education and value education and a preschool teacher were received. Then, all the stories were reanalyzed with the table in question. After the expert opinions were asked again, all the stories were reanalyzed again with the QSR NVivo 11 program to minimize the findings which might have been missed and the codes were given their final shape with software support. After the completion of the study, 3 randomly selected books were analyzed by an area expert within the framework of the categories determined by the researchers and the approval of the area expert was received.

3. Findings

3.1 Findings on Honest Behavior Examples

The frequency of honest behavior examples in the stories in the study group, which is the first of the sub-problems of the research, is examined under this sub-category. The number of honest behavior examples given a place in the analyzed picture books and online stories is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of positive behavior examples in terms of honesty in the analyzed stories

Behavior Classification	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Honest Behavior Examples	48	41	7

As it can be seen in Table 1, a total of 48 honest behavior examples were determined, 41 being in picture books and seven in the online stories. Some of the honest behavior examples in the analyzed stories are given below with direct quotations:

“One of the best sides of honesty is never to take something that does not belong to you.” (PS 6)

“-I’m sorry, sir! My friends and I were playing. I hit the ball in the wrong way. It hit your window. I’m sorry,” he said.” (PS 7)

“Erdal honestly managed the match from the beginning until the end and the team of the other school won the match by playing wonderful football.” (PS 9)

In some of the books, the reasons for the character's honest behavior are included. The determined reasons are given under the next subtitle.

3.2 Findings Related to the Reasons for Honest Behaviors

The second sub-problem of the study is “What was shown as the reason for behaving honestly?” Findings related to the question are presented in this sub-category. While dealing with the reasons for honest behaviors, the situations in which it is necessary to behave honestly are stated clearly and the reasons for the changing of the characters who were not honest before but then behaved honestly are given in separate tables. The findings related to the reasons for behaving honestly are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Reasons for behaving honestly in the stories

Reason for honesty	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
To end a rude behavior someone is subjected to	1	0
A mother being able to see everything	1	0
The trust of the elderly	1	0
Not telling the truth making one feel bad	1	0
To have good friends	1	0
To take responsibility	1	0
Lying not being right	1	0
Older people getting angrier when lies are told	1	0
TOTAL	8	0

As it can be seen in Table 2, to end a rude behavior someone else is subjected to, a mother being able to see everything, the trust of the elderly, lying making one feel bad, making good friends, to take responsibility, lying not being right and older people getting angrier when lies are told were the reasons for honesty determined in the analyzed picture books which were clearly stated. The researchers found that no reason was given for the honest behavior of the characters in the online stories which are in the study group of the research. An example of a direct quotation related to the coding of the presented reasons for behaving honestly is given below:

Sample quotation about lying making one feel bad:

“- If I don’t tell the truth, I would feel bad. Grandma Tumos don’t have to be mad at me. I went to her and told her the truth, she said.” (PS 16)

Some of the characters in the stories of the study group displayed only honest behavior throughout the story and some displayed dishonest behaviors, whereas some others first displayed dishonest and then honest behaviors. Table 3 shows the reasons why the characters who initially did not behave honestly in the analyzed stories later behaved honestly and the findings regarding the frequency of these reasons.

Table 3: Reasons for the characters to behave dishonestly at first and to behave honestly later

The reasons why characters who do not behave honestly at first behaved honestly later	Number seen in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Exposition of a lie	4	3	1
Advice, suggestion	3	3	0
The threat of being punished	1	1	0
Realizing that telling the truth is the best thing	1	1	0
Getting unjustly accused	1	1	0
Regret	1	1	0
Realizing that the lies being told were stupid	1	1	0
Remorse	1	0	1
Not believing in a lie	1	0	1
Realizing the consequences of a lie	1	1	0
Getting harmed	1	1	0
TOTAL	16	13	3

Table 3 shows the most frequent reason the characters who did not behave honestly at first behaved honestly later: the exposition of a lie. This reason was found four times. In the changing of the dishonest characters, only one or both factors stated in Table 3 were effective at times. Characters in a story were threatened with being punished after a lie was exposed; a character in another story realized that telling the truth is the best thing to do after he was accused unjustly and a character in yet another story realized that he had told a stupid lie and his mother gave him advice. The following are some examples from the stories which point out the reason why the dishonest characters changed to behave honestly:

Example quotation about a threat to be punished:

“You either admit your fault or your punishment will be doubled, he said.” (PB 3)

The researchers found that the analyzed stories included the consequences of honesty, as well as providing reasons for honest behavior in some cases.

3.3 Findings Related to The Consequences of Behaving Honestly

In the third sub-problem of the study, researchers examined the consequences of behaving honestly in stories. In the analyzed stories, behaving honestly was given place to as the character’s benefitting himself/herself and others, whereas the positive emotions caused by behaving honestly felt by the character or others were given place to in some of the stories. The findings on the benefits caused by the honest behavior of the character in the analyzed stories are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Benefits of behaving honestly for the honest character

Benefit	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Being rewarded	6	4	2
Making one realize the mistake through positive wording	4	1	3
Being appreciated	3	3	0
Being forgiven	2	2	0
Reputation	2	2	0
Being congratulated	2	2	0
Being loved	2	2	0
Experiencing fewer problems	1	1	0
Being a person people like to be with	1	1	0
Assuming a duty that makes one happy	1	1	0
Protecting oneself against dangers	1	1	0
Getting a lost item back	1	1	0
TOTAL	26	21	5

In Table 4, the most seen benefit of behaving honestly for the honest characters was being rewarded in the whole study group (n=6). Example of direct quotations about the codes of the benefits of behaving honestly for the characters is given below:

Example quotation about being rewarded:

“-You can choose any fish you want as a reward for your honesty, said Mr. Claw.” (PB 14)

In the analyzed stories, examples were seen about behaving honestly causing both material and moral benefits for the honest character were seen. Among the stories in the study group, it was seen that there were instances

where besides the benefits of behaving honestly for the character, the benefits for the others were also given place. The benefits of behaving honestly for other people are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Benefits of behaving honestly for other people

Benefit	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Learning about the truth	2	2	0
The World is a more beautiful and just place	1	1	0
Preventing innocent people from being accused and punished	1	1	0
Preventing misunderstandings	1	1	0
TOTAL	5	5	0

As it can be seen in Table 5, the benefits of behaving honestly for others were seen 5 times in the picture books. The benefits of behaving honestly for others were not seen in the online stories. Among the stories in the study group, the identified example about the benefits of behaving honestly for others is given below:
Example quotation about learning about the truth:

“Thus, others will learn about your real emotions and thoughts.” (PB 6)

The positive consequences of behaving honestly were sometimes shown through positive emotions. In the stories in the study group, the findings of the emotions the honest character feels are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Emotions created by behaving honestly in the honest character

Emotion seen in the character	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Happiness/Joy	8	7	1
Relaxing	4	3	1
Feeling brave	1	1	0
Feeling good	1	1	0
Having self-assurance	1	1	0
TOTAL	15	13	2

It can be seen in Table 6 that, the most seen emotion as a result of honesty in the analyzed stories is happiness which was given place to 8 times. An example about the codes of the emotions behaving honestly creates in the characters is given below with quotations from the stories:

Example quotation about happiness/joy:

“Being truthful has made me happier.” (PB 20)

The honest behavior of a character led to positive consequences such as creating positive emotions in others as well. In the stories in the study group, the findings of the emotions created in other characters by the honest behavior of characters are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Emotions created in other characters as a result of behaving honestly

Emotion seen in other characters	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Happiness/Joy	5	4	1
Admiration	1	1	0
Enjoyment	1	1	0
Overcoming anger	1	1	0
TOTAL	8	7	1

When Table 7 is analyzed, the most seen emotion created in others by the honest behavior of a character was happiness/joy (n=5). It was seen in the eight examples that behaving honestly contributed to developing positive emotions in others. Example of direct quotations about the codes of emotions behaving honestly causes in other people is given below:

Example quotation about overcoming anger:

“-How nice it is that you told the truth, she said. I don’t feel like being angry at you. How can you be angry at someone who tells the truth?” (PB 16)

In the stories in the study group, besides the examples of honest behavior, there are examples of dishonest behavior as well.

3.4 Findings About Examples of Dishonest Behavior

In the fourth sub-problem of the study, the researchers examined the findings on the frequency of dishonest behavior in the stories. The number of dishonest behavior examples given a place in the analyzed picture books and online stories is given in Table 8.

Table 8: Number of negative behaviors in terms of honesty in the analyzed stories

Behavior Classification	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Examples of Dishonest Behavior	73	62	11

As it can be seen in Table 8, a total of 73 examples of dishonest behavior were found, 62 being in the picture books and 11 in the online stories. Some quotations which involve examples of being dishonest in the analyzed stories are given below:

“They hid their axes and pretended to be crying. They shouted and asked for help for the Phoenix.” (PB 1)”

“Should we hide the broken pieces of the vase in the garden shed?” (PB 10)

The distribution of the characters’ state of being honest in the analyzed stories are shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Distribution of all the characters according to their state of being honest

As it can be seen in Figure 1, the rate of characters who behaved honestly throughout the story is 30%, the rate of characters who behaved dishonestly is 45% and the rate of characters who behaved dishonestly at first but then behaved honestly is 25%. In some stories, characters displayed honest or dishonest behavior more than once. Some of the dishonest behaviors seen in the analyzed stories in the study were justified.

3.5 Findings About the Reasons for Dishonest Behavior

In the fifth sub-problem of the study, it was examined what reasons were given for dishonest behavior. The reasons shown for dishonest behaviors determined in picture books and online stories and the frequency of seeing these reasons are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Reasons given for dishonest behaviors in the stories

Reason for behaving dishonestly	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
The wish to enjoy oneself	6	6	0
The wish to influence others	3	2	1
The wish for unearned income	3	2	1
Fear	3	2	1
The wish to drive a wedge between friends	2	2	0
The wish to avoid being scolded	2	2	0
The wish to take something away from someone's hands	2	1	1
Avoiding problems	1	1	0
Avoiding duties	1	1	0
The wish to preserve reputation	1	1	0
Jealousy	1	1	0
Embarrassment	1	1	0
Lying being easier	1	1	0
TOTAL	27	23	4

In Table 9, it can be seen that reasons for dishonest behavior were seen in 27 situations. In the analyzed stories, the most seen reason for behaving dishonestly for the dishonest characters is displaying dishonest behavior to enjoy themselves found 6 times. The example of quotations shown as clear reasons for the identified dishonest behaviors is given below:

Example quotation for the wish to influence others:

“Cheetah wished to appear like a famous person...” (PB 21)

The results of negative behaviors in terms of honesty in the stories in the study group are given in the next section.

3.6 Findings About Examples of Dishonest Behavior

Characters who were dishonest in the stories analyzed in the study sometimes received damage due to these behaviors. The identified damages are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Damages characters received as a result of behaving dishonestly

The damage the character receives for not being honest	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Loss of trust	4	4	0
Being punished	3	3	0
Losing material things	3	2	1
Losing friends	2	2	0
Physical damage	2	2	0
Changing place of residence	2	2	0
Loss of reputation	1	1	0
TOTAL	17	16	1

As can be seen in Table 10, characters who displayed dishonest behaviors received damage in a total of 17 instances. The most seen damage the dishonest characters received was losing people’s trust found 4 times in the stories. The examples of quotations from the stories coded under the sub-category of the damage the character receives for not being honest are given below:

Example quotation about losing trust:

“The other animals lost the trust of the others and received the heaviest punishment.” (PB 3)

Example quotation about changing place of residence:

“As our liar shepherd set out on his way to work in another village, he swore that he would never lie again.” (PB 11)

In picture books and online stories analyzed in the study, sometimes a character’s dishonest behavior caused other characters to receive damage. The findings about the damages others received are given in Table 11.

Table 11: Damages received by others as a result of dishonest behavior

Damage received by others as a result of dishonest behavior	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Changing place of residence	5	5	0
Being punished	3	3	0
Receiving physical damage	3	3	0
Friends being at odds with each other	2	2	0
Financial damage	2	1	1
TOTAL	15	14	1

As it can be seen in Table 11, the most seen damage given by dishonest characters to the others is changing the place of residence which was found 5 times. An example of quotations from the stories coded under the sub-category of damages given to others by behaving dishonestly is given below:

Example quotation about being punished:

“Since Zeynep denied pinching Kaan, the teacher punished Tolga instead of her.” (PB 13)

Dishonest behaviors caused both the dishonest characters and the others to receive damage in various situations. In addition, emotions created with the effect of behaving dishonestly were also given a place in the stories. The emotions felt directly or indirectly by the dishonest character in picture books and online stories analyzed in the study and the frequency of seeing these emotions in the stories are given in Table 12.

Table 12: Emotions felt by the character as a result of behaving dishonestly

Emotions are created in the character as a result of behaving dishonestly	Number in all stories	Number of being seen in picture books	Number in online stories
Embarrassment	6	5	1
Feeling bad	5	3	2
Enjoyment	4	4	0
Regret	4	4	0
Happiness	3	3	0
Sadness	3	1	2
Feeling anxious	1	1	0
Feeling uneasy	1	1	0
Being surprised	1	1	0
Remorse	1	0	1
Feeling lonely	1	1	0
TOTAL	30	24	6

It can be seen in Table 12 that, 30 situations were found in which the character creates certain emotions as a result of behaving dishonestly. The most frequently seen emotions as a result of dishonest behaviors of the character are embarrassment which was seen 6 times and feeling bad which was seen 5 times. The examples of quotations from the stories coded about the sub-category of the emotions created by the character himself as a result of behaving dishonestly:

Example quotation about feeling bad:

“I felt very bad for blaming my brother.” (PB 16)

Example quotation on enjoyment:

“The snake laughed at the situation it was watching in secret. He enjoyed his words to be so easily believed in.” (PB 2)

The emotions created directly or indirectly in others as a result of the dishonest behavior of a character in the analyzed picture books and online stories and the frequency with which these emotions were underlined in the stories are given in Table 13.

Table 13: Emotions created in others as a result of behaving dishonestly

Emotions are created in others due to not behaving honestly	Number in all stories	Number in picture books	Number in online stories
Sadness	14	12	2
Anger / Rage	10	10	0
Surprise	6	6	0
Dislike	2	2	0
Frustration	1	1	0
Hopelessness	1	1	0
Uneasiness	1	1	0
TOTAL	35	33	2

As it can be seen in Table 13, the most frequently emphasized emotions created in others directly or indirectly by a character in a story were sadness found 14 times and anger/rage found 10 times. The examples of quotations from stories coded under the titles of emotions created in other characters due to not behaving honestly:

Example quotation about sadness:

“It made me sad that you lied not to do your homework...” (PB 19)

4. Conclusion and Discussion

This study was carried out with the purpose of how the subject of honesty is dealt with in Turkish stories with the theme of honesty written for preschool children. As a result of analyses to determine how much place was given to examples of honest behavior which is the first sub-problem of the study, 41 behaviors were found which can be positive examples related to the value of honesty in picture books (see, Table 1). It was seen that the number of examples of honest behavior is close to the number obtained in Dirican and Dağlıoğlu's (2014) study. 38 expressions related to the value of honesty were found in In Dirican and Dağlıoğlu's study (2014) carried out to identify what the basic humane values are in picture books written by Turkish writers intended for the acquisition of value by children in the 3-6 age group and the rate of these being given place to in the 135 books which were analyzed and it was stated that the value of honesty is one of the least mentioned value in the analyzed picture books.

The second sub-problem of the study is related to the identification of reasons for honest behavior. For honesty which is expected to be displayed without appealing to any dishonest behaviors in the case of a moral dilemma, 8 reasons were seen in 31 stories (see, Table 2). When these reasons were analyzed, it was seen that the reasons shown for honesty in the stories in the study group carry in terms of their sources since there are both individual inner reasons and exterior reasons. Among the reasons which cause a change in characters who first acted dishonestly and then honestly, regret and remorse which took place on their own were seen once each. The sources of the change in the characters are mostly exterior in the stories in the study group (see, Table 3). In Fu, Evans, Xu and Lee's (2012) study with children aged 3, 4 and 5, it was concluded that preschool children can

understand bluffs and tell strategic lies. With this finding that even small children can tell strategic lies, it can be considered that they can interpret the character's reason for behaving honestly as strategic. However, no studies were found which analyzed the effects of reasons for honesty shown in the stories in the literature on the honesty of children.

The third sub-problem of the study is related to the identification of the consequences of honest behaviors. According to the results of the analyses done with this purpose (see, Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7), it was seen that behaving honestly has positive effects on both the character and the others. It was seen that morally rewarding and positive reinforcers directed at the character by the others such as being rewarded, being appreciated, being congratulated, being loved are high in number (see, Table 4). According to Erikson's Psychosocial Development Stages, it is in particular very important to get the approval of the parents for children who are in a period of guilt in terms of taking initiative (Butcher, Mineka and Hooley, 2014). When taken from this point of view, it can be considered to stories in which feedback such as being rewarded, being appreciated, being congratulated and being loved which show that the approval of the parents is received which the child views as important or is influential in the development of the child can be effective on the child. While a behavior is evaluated as moral by children who are considered to be at a pre-tradition level in terms of Kohlberg's Moral Development Stages, the consequences of that particular behavior carry great importance (Kohlberg, 1975). For that reason, it can be stated that giving place to the positive results of the values and behaviors which are desired to be acquired by the children through the stories in the stories would be beneficial.

As a result of the analyses done to determine the frequency of examples of honest behavior in the stories in the study group which is the fourth sub-problem of the study, it was seen that the stories contained numerous and different examples of dishonest behavior (see, Table 8). In Lee, Cameron, Doucette and Talwar's study (2002) carried out with children aged 3-4, it was determined that the children tend to believe the irrational lies told by the characters in the stories. When especially the life experiences, cognitive and moral development characteristics of 3-4-year-old children are taken into consideration, children may not develop the desired attitude towards the lies presented in the stories.

It was seen that almost all of the dishonest behaviors were justified with egocentric thought as a result of the analyses on determining the reasons for dishonest behavior in the stories in the study group which is the fifth sub-problem of the study (see, Table 9). As it is possible to come across study findings which show that preschool children lie for selfish reasons (Buccioli and Piovesan, 2011; Fu et al., 2012), there are studies which show that preschool children lie out of politeness, not to hurt others or for the well-being of others as well. Williams, Kirmayer, Simon and Talwar (2013) determined in their study with children aged 6-7 that children both lie out of selfishness and out of politeness and that their rate of telling lies to adult strangers is higher compared to telling lies to their parents. In the studies, while it was seen that preschool children can tell prosocial lies, it is noteworthy that there aren't lies in the stories in the study group which can be defined as white lies which are told not to hurt others or for the well-being of others.

The sixth sub-problem of the study carried the aim of determining the consequences of dishonest behaviors in the stories in the study group. As a result of the analyses done for that purpose, it was seen that dishonest behaviors both harm the character and others (see, Tables 10 and 11). When the emotions created by dishonest behaviors were analyzed, it was seen that the character creates both positive and negative emotions, whereas creates only negative emotions in others (see, Tables 12 and 13). Dishonest characters having fun-laughing were seen 4 times and statements about them being happy were seen 3 times. Although these characters face negative consequences at the end of the stories, it can be stated that it is possible to transmit the message that a person can be happy through dishonest behaviors due to the children's line of thought, "I can avoid the mistake this character did, I can hide my lie," or if the narration is cut short at a point for any reason where the character is having fun. However, when the results are evaluated as a whole, it can be seen that dishonest behaviors are mostly negative.

Another finding of the study is that dishonest characters were given more place in the stories in the study group compared to honest characters (see, Graphic 1). Smith and Guerny (1977) determined in their study carried out with 3rd and 6th-grade students that, the number of children who identified themselves with the honest adult characters in the film they watched is much higher compared to children who identified themselves with dishonest characters. Although a study analyzes the relationship with the identification children form with the characters in the fictional stories they watch or listen to and honesty, it is possible to find studies on the relationship between the trust felt for the character and honesty. In Li, Heyman, Xu and Lee's study (2014) with children aged 3-5, it was determined that it was possible to observe the relationship of honesty-trust in the form of trusting honest characters in children aged 5 whereas this was not observed clearly in children aged 3 and 4. This finding can be interpreted as the need to carefully choose the traits of the characters in the stories to be read in particular to children in the younger age groups.

It was concluded through the comparison of the findings of the first, third, fourth and sixth sub-problems of the study that examples about dishonest behaviors were given place to more compared to examples of honest behavior (see, Tables 1 and 8); benefits of honesty and harms of dishonesty were given in very close numbers (see, Tables 4, 5, 10 and 11) and that negative emotions caused by dishonesty were given more place to compared to emotions caused by honesty (see, Tables 6, 7, 12 and 13). When the findings were evaluated in general, it was concluded that the framework formed with the sum of the findings obtained with the stories in the study group underlined "dishonesty and its negative consequences," more than "honesty and its positive consequences." According to the findings of the study carried out by Lee et al. (2014), the story titled *George Washington and the Cherry Tree* which emphasizes the positive consequences of honest behaviors increased the honest behaviors of preschool children, whereas the stories titled *Pinocchio* and *The Liar Shepherd* were not effective in reducing dishonest behaviors in children. As a result, it can be stated that it should be taken into consideration that the evaluations related to these examples may not be in the desired form when negative examples are given in terms of honesty when preschool children's life experiences, cognitive and moral developments are taken into account. In this respect, rather than expecting children to make inferences about behaving honestly by considering the negative consequences of examples of dishonest behavior given a place in the stories prepared for this age group, it may be more beneficial to deal with the value of honesty through the examples of honest behavior. On the other hand, teachers and parents need to evaluate the positive and negative behaviors when choosing stories dealing with honesty. While dealing with the issue of honesty through stories, teachers and parents can be suggested to guide children to think about the stories and do evaluations about the stories.

This study in which stories written for preschool children dealing with honesty has certain limitations. The results of the study are limited to picture books and online stories dealing with honesty and written for preschool children and qualitative and quantitative content analyses carried out using the qualitative research approach.

Some suggestions can be made about the application and future studies in light of the results and the limitations of the study. While preparing picture books for children dealing with honesty, the opinions of experts in the area of child development and children's literature should be taken. Instead of the negative consequences of being honest in stories with the theme of honesty, the positive consequences of honesty should be underlined. Characters with which the children can identify themselves should be selected when creating stories with the theme of honesty. In stories on other values used in preschool education, the researchers are suggested to analyze how these values are dealt with in these stories. An experimental study can be carried out on the effects of the environment being realistic or unrealistic in stories read in terms of the honest behaviors of children. An experimental study can be carried out on the effects of the person being affected by the positive or negative consequences of behaviors depicted in stories with the theme of honesty read to the children being the character himself or another character on the behaviors of children.

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